
65. Hot Jupiters and star clustering

THE DISCOVERY OF EXOPLANETS, planets orbiting stars beyond our own solar system, confirmed in 1995, catalysed a new research field in astronomy, viz. the observation, and the theoretical and computational interpretation, of the formation and evolution of exoplanets.

Amongst many pioneering observational initiatives, and thousands of research papers, the launch of NASA's Kepler space telescope in 2009 arguably marked the next revolution in the field. In more than nine years of operation, Kepler discovered close to 3000 planets, a rich variety of planetary systems and system architectures, providing the foundation for thousands of scientific papers related to their discovery and characterisation.

Today, Gaia is contributing a major observational advance in the understanding of our Galaxy and, specifically in this context, of exoplanet systems. By determining the distances and space motions of their host stars, Gaia is precisely characterising their host star luminosities, their location in the observational Hertzsprung–Russell diagram and, via their inferred radii, the physical radii of the transiting planets themselves.

There is also the anticipated discovery, directly with Gaia, although still perhaps some years hence, of thousands of systems from their astrometric motions.

ONE OF MANY AREAS in which Gaia is contributing, and which nicely illustrates the complex foundations upon which our theories depend, is that of the origin of the perplexing class of exoplanet known as 'hot Jupiters'. These are massive gas giant planets, somewhat like Jupiter or Saturn, but which orbit surprisingly close to their host star, typically within about 0.1 astronomical units (Mercury orbits at just under 0.4 au), corresponding to extremely short periods of around 3–9 days.

In situ formation of these hot Jupiters seems implausible: in models of core accretion, both the available protoplanetary disk mass, and the opening of disk gaps, appear to preclude their growth, while in models of direct gravitational collapse due to disk instability, the gas cools too slowly for the resulting spiral structures to fragment into bound clumps.

These sorts of considerations support the idea that hot Jupiters must have arrived at their present locations from their region of formation beyond the snow line (beyond around 3 au), where solid material is inferred to be abundant in the form of condensed ices.

Assuming that they formed at much larger distances from the host star, there are then two main hypotheses as to how they arrived at their present locations: either via disk-driven inward migration, or through the generation of a highly eccentric orbit with small pericentre, followed by its tidal damping and orbital circularisation.

And there are at least three plausible mechanisms which might generate such high-eccentricity orbits: planet–planet encounters leading to orbit 'scattering', resonant orbit changes due to a distant stellar companion (the 'Lidov–Kozai mechanism'), or as a result of close stellar encounters, perhaps in a young star cluster.

This is not the place to describe these processes, and the evidence for them, in detail. Here, I will look exclusively at how Gaia is helping to clarify the role of close stellar encounters in the possible formation of these strange giant planets, so close to their host stars.

IT HAS BEEN DIFFICULT to argue convincingly that the existence of at least some of these hot Jupiters has been affected by close stellar encounters, in part because stellar groups disperse, at least in 3d space, within less than a billion years, much shorter than the ages of most known exoplanets.

An early approach to this problem, using the Gaia DR2 data, was by Winter et al. (2020). They identified old co-moving stellar groups around exoplanet host stars, and argued that system architectures have a strong dependence on local stellar clustering in position–velocity 'phase space', viz. while individual stars born in an open star cluster may long since have 'disappeared' into the field star population, evidence for their common origin may still be preserved in their space motions.

Indeed, propagating the space motions of some 'runaway' stars backwards in time, can often point back to their origin in some ancient star cluster.

After accounting for the star's age, mass, and metallicity, Winter et al. found significant differences in properties between exoplanet systems residing in phase-space density enhancements, and those in the field population. Median semi-major axes and orbit periods in the overdense regions are 0.09 au and 9.6 d, compared to 0.81 au and 154 d for planets around field stars.

They found that 'hot Jupiters' preferentially exist in phase-space overdensity regions, suggesting that their extremely 'tight' (short-period) orbits arise from environmental perturbations, rather than from inward migration or planet–planet scattering, i.e. star clustering is a key factor in determining the architectures, and indeed the atmospheric properties, of exoplanet systems.

WINTER ET AL. were careful to point out that a similar sort of 'velocity clustering' can also be generated later in the planetary system's lifetime by other dynamical features within our Galaxy.

Many recent results, starting with the release of Gaia DR2 in 2018, have confirmed that the phase-space distribution of disk stars (i.e. their dependence on position *and* velocity) shows considerable sub-structure, with waves, ripples, and streams. They are generated by resonances and instabilities driven by our Galaxy's central bar and by its spiral arms, or by the passages of satellite galaxies through the Galactic disk which can drive spiral and vertical perturbations. Within these structures, star velocities are correlated over distances of several kpc.

Kruijssen et al. (2021) used the Gaia DR2 data (including the radial velocities to yield the full space motions) to show that at least some of their inferred overdensities correspond to such kpc-scale 'ripples' and 'streams' in the Galactic disk.

Another recent and relevant Gaia discovery is the so-called 'phase-space spiral', a prominent feature in the space spanned by the height above the Galactic mid-plane and the star's vertical velocity. This has been attributed to a recent crossing of our Galaxy's disk by the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy. Kruijssen et al. (2021) found that exoplanet systems associated with this phase-space spiral have a ratio of hot Jupiters to cold Jupiters that is 10 times higher than in field systems.

Another of their findings was that the ratio of hot Jupiters to cold Jupiters within any of these overdensity regions appears to increase with stellar age over timescales of billions of years, consistent with the lifetimes of these Galactic-driven overdensities. In turn, this suggests that planetary system properties are not only affected by stellar clustering in their immediate surroundings, but by processes on a Galactic scale throughout their evolution.

More details of the perturbation models are given by, e.g. Rodet et al. (2021) and Rodet & Lai (2022).

As Kruijssen et al. (2021) conclude, these new Gaia results imply that planetary systems are not only affected by stellar clustering in their immediate surroundings, but by processes on a Galactic scale throughout their evolution. It remains as a challenge for the future to establish a complete census of the physical processes at work, which will require combining studies of planet formation and evolution, star (cluster) formation, Galactic dynamics, and galaxy formation and evolution.

FURTHER PIECES of the puzzle as to how exoplanet system architectures are related to a system's passage through the Galaxy have been explored by Daia et al. (2021). They used the Gaia and Kepler data to divide main-sequence star systems into three groups according to their velocities compared to the local standard.

They found that high-velocity planet hosts (with local velocities above about 50 km s^{-1}) are associated with a higher fraction of multi-planet systems (and of lower than average eccentricity), consistent with the higher velocity stars actually experiencing fewer gravitationally perturbing events as they moved through the Galaxy. Low-velocity stars (with space velocities below about $20\text{--}30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) appear to be more strongly perturbed by the effects of stellar clustering.

IN THIS FAST-MOVING FIELD, the big picture being consolidated by Gaia is of a highly complex Galaxy, in terms of both its spatial and velocity sub-structures, whose characterisation will allow a more detailed picture of exoplanet systems, their formation and evolution, and how they have been modified during their billion year journeys through our Milky Way Galaxy.